

THE ESSENCE OF DIDACTIC EDUCATION IN THE PROCESS OF PEDAGOGICAL COMMUNICATION OF THE TEACHER TO THE PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

It is important to ensure the quality and efficiency of the education system, for which, first of all, the culture and style of communication between teachers, professors and students must be properly organized. In some cases, improper choice of communication methods in educators, insufficient development of communication skills have a negative impact on the quality of the educational process and the motivation of students' learning activities. The realization of the pedagogical potential of the culture of communication is largely determined by the personal qualities of the teacher.

Pedagogical communication is a system, methods and skills of interaction between the teacher and the student body, consisting of the exchange of information on the content, educational interaction and the organization of mutual cooperation. The educator emerges as the initiator of this process and organizes and directs it. While assessing the educational and didactic significance of pedagogical communication, A.N. Leontev makes the following points. Active pedagogical communication is the key to the knowledge and learning of students in the educational process of the teacher, the pedagogical team in general, and the creative nature of educational activities, creating the best conditions for the formation of the student's personality. providing an

acceptable emotional environment in education, including the prevention of psychological barriers, ensuring the proper management of socio-psychological processes in the community of children, and in the educational process is an important tool that creates opportunities for the teacher to use his or her pedagogical skills wisely. The didactic and especially pedagogical functions of pedagogical activity cannot be carried out effectively enough without the organization of a fruitful communication process between the teacher and the student body. Thus, communication in pedagogical activity:

- First, as a means of solving learning problems.

- Secondly, as a system of socio-psychological support of the educational process.

- Thirdly, as a way to organize a certain system of interaction between teachers and students, which allows for the successful conduct of education and upbringing.

- Fourth, it emerges as a process without which the individual characteristics of the student cannot be nurtured.

Pedagogical communication has a dynamic character that corresponds to the logic of the pedagogical process. The following stages are distinguished in the structure of pedagogical communication: 1. Modeling (forecasting) - the implementation of a specific planning of the communicative structure of interaction in accordance with the pedagogical tasks. 2. Organization of direct communication (communicative attack) - the educator takes the initiative, the technology of rapid involvement of the group. 3. Communication management - ensuring the communicability of the methods of influence used (support of student initiative, organization of student initiative, dialogue, o 4. Correction of the course and results of the implemented pedagogical communication technology. This stage is often called the feedback phase in communication and the solution of the communicative task. corresponds to the final stage.

V.A. Kan-Kalik emphasizes that pedagogical communication is organized by the methods of relations and interaction, and classifies them as follows:

1) Communication based on interest in collaborative creative work. In a

dialogue based on an interest in collaborative creative work, the educator takes a positive approach to learners and work.

2) communication based on friendly relations. Communication based on friendship is similar to the type of communication discussed above. Some educators misunderstand friendly communication and go too far. There must be a certain distance between the teacher and the student. The teacher's culture and pedagogical tactics play an important role in determining this distance.

3) communication that keeps teachers and learners at a certain distance. Distance communication is also not effective. Still, this is a common style. There are certain boundaries between educators and students, which can be described as: "I know - you do not know", "Do what I say - I'm older, I have more experience, we can not be equated ". This style is closer to authoritarianism, which from the outside seems to help to carry out orderly activities, but does not give high results.

4) communication based on intimidation. A high-level form of communication that keeps teachers and learners at a certain distance is intimidating. It embodies negative attitudes toward students and authoritarian rule. Examples of this style are: "Listen carefully, or I'll put two", "I'll show you your days". This style creates a negative atmosphere during training.

It is well known that man is not born into the world with a fully formed program of character and moral qualities, that his inherent qualities and moral norms are the product of social life and family upbringing. At all times, people have

named the central streets, squares and alleys after the brave sons of the nation.

Among them are not only commanders who have shown courage, but also those who have worked hard in the fields of science, culture, art and literature. So courage does not choose a profession. It is a product of the socio-spiritual environment, purposeful and consistent upbringing. Therefore, by further improving the family and school environment, our children can be brought up with confidence and influence.

First and foremost, students need to be taught to overcome fear, hesitation, and cowardice. Because you can't teach a child to swim without putting him in the water. Indeed, it is difficult to overcome the fear and intimidation of students without trying them in situations that require courage and bravery.

In *The Nightmare*, Kaykovus (11th century) focuses on teaching children a trade, and in his advice to his child, he also addresses the issue of the culture of parental and teacher treatment of children. For example, he warns that it is possible for a parent to influence a child through a teacher in order to instill knowledge and moral qualities in their child: "... If every science teacher beats (a child) for education, you (Father) show mercy, let them strike, because a young boy learns to be polite and does not learn voluntarily. But if the child is rude and you get angry because of it, don't hit him with your hand, be afraid with the teacher's stick. Let the children be disciplined by the teachers, so that your son will not be angry with you.

If we want to raise our young people to be brave, courageous and fearless, we need a different approach. Because the

romantic stage of the history of upbringing, the upbringing of courage is over. Developed countries have already entered its technological stage.

It is up to the parents to bring up the students wisely, wisely, actively and successfully, bravely and courageously. We should try to equip them with the most advanced knowledge. Now it is necessary to create a new principle of education - the technology of formation of the most important qualities that serve the interests of the individual, the state and the nation. Because knowledge is material, virtue is fire. It is impossible to apply modern knowledge and technologies and make new discoveries without a burning heart, a strong will, a strong spirit, infinite courage and common sense.

Therefore, educators need to educate students to be the most confident young people on earth. If we are willing and able to do this, we can become one of the leading nations. Otherwise, they will have to live on inventions, not products.

The father of faith is the mind, the mother is the heart. Confidence occurs in the mind, and then in words and deeds. That is why the Uzbek national pedagogical authorities have always said that mental education is a sacred duty of teachers. Our great enlightened ancestor Abdullah Avloni said the following about the education of thought:

Fikr, agar yaxshi tarbiya topsa,
translation: The idea is that if you get a good upbringing,

Xanjar, olmosdan bo'lur o'tkir.
The dagger is sharper than a diamond.

Fikrning oynasi olursa zang,

If there is a window of thought,
rust,

Ruhi ravshan zamir o'lur
benur.¹

The spirit of enlightenment dies

The more educators there are, the more methods and tools are used, the faster the goal will be achieved. Pedagogy does not create its methods from nothing, it does not invent them. He selects from life real factors of human behavior, responsible for the organization of student life in a pedagogical way, uses them as methods of pedagogical influence in educational work. Methods of pedagogical influence on the socially useful activities of students consists of a system of tools used for pedagogically purposeful organization. These tools focus on the learner's personality, stimulate students' behavior, and make their difficult and complex tasks a source of joy, a source of creative pleasure, and their personal interests.

Before moving on to a separate description of the methods of pedagogical influence, let us consider the general rules of their successful application; A prerequisite for the effective use of pedagogical methods is the true humanity of the teacher's attitude to students. Methods of pedagogical influence are not a set of purely professional tools in the hands of those who are indifferent to the fate of their students, they are a community, a single aspiration, a living relationship of living people united by a common responsibility.

People who make toughness and ruthlessness, formal administration the norm in their dealings with students,

cannot be true educators. In our context, only a path aimed at developing and strengthening the friendly relations between teachers and students can be the basis of pedagogical influence. Therefore, the use of this or that method in any case not only leads to a small change in the activities of students, but also always actively contributes to the development of relations between teachers and students.

The second general rule of thumb for pedagogical influence is that it must be reasonably prepared. Its application implies the existence of conditions for its implementation. The real potential of students, taking into account their ability to perform tasks that are encouraged by the educator, is the essence of a personal approach to the use of pedagogical tools. Sometimes, one or another pedagogical influence is ineffective because the educator does not provide the necessary material means for its implementation. For example, not all students are provided with the tools they need to work, and the teacher asks them to complete the next task. Consistent implementation of general principles, such as taking into account the age and individual characteristics of students, is also important in the implementation of pedagogical influence. As mentioned above, the correctness of this or that method of educational process. the success of selection and its application requires the educator to know and take into account the pedagogical situation. The pedagogical situation has its own characteristics for the methods of pedagogical influence. Here are the key conditions for the successful application of pedagogical methods. This is, first of all, the relationship of the educator with the pupil.

¹ Abdullah Avloni's work "Turkish Gulistan or Morality" together with "Education of Thought".

These relationships are not permanent, they develop and enrich in the process of interaction. It is clear that in a friendly relationship, one way of influencing will be effective, and in a neutral or negative relationship (which can also be the case), a different way, a different form will be needed.

Then one of the important conditions is the attitude of the students to the activities suggested by the teacher. It is well known that forcing a student to do easy and decisive work is one thing, but getting him to do serious, extraordinary work is quite another.

Much depends on the position of the student in the team. He may still be new, unaware of his traditions and the actions of his friends. The team may have experience in all areas of life. In the first case as well as in the second case, the method of influencing the pupil can not be the same. They may be angry at something. This, in turn, is the basis for choosing the form of exposure.

The connection between the pedagogical situation and the form of pedagogical influence it requires is important. Understanding this connection allows educators to be more effective in their actions, to develop them consciously.

Considering the single pedagogical requirements, we have said that only in our humane society can the pedagogical demand become an effective method of education in strengthening the spiritual and political unity of the people. As the teacher works with students and organizes their activities, he encourages some of the students' actions with his instructions. In the process, he gives them specific feedback, reprimands or encourages them,

and concludes. While some of his commands are short and concise and play the role of subtle coercion, others take the form of broader explanatory instructions. Some were created solely to force students to work, while others arose out of the need to adjust students' acquisition of certain skills and competencies; while some stop students from doing unnecessary and wrong things, others reinforce and support their successful actions. All the instructions and explanations, comments and reprimands given by the teacher refer to the various forms of demand, which is the most important way to exert pedagogical influence. Therefore, it is safe to say that it is impossible to imagine the organization of educational and socially useful activities of students without the demands of the teacher.

An experienced educator will accompany the students with an extensive program of action, knowing exactly what each of their students will do when. After all, requirements are only a means of implementing this program in their actions and behavior.

The style of communication chosen by the educator is especially important in the early stages of working with the student body, in the early lessons. At this stage, how the work in the group goes, how precisely this or that action is performed by the students, how the teacher's relationship with the student begins to develop, the students consider him a respected partner - their leader. Whether they admit it or not - it all depends on the requirements of the educator.

Thus, in the early stages of working with students and in the organization of new types of their activities, the

requirements of the teacher are an important means of stimulating the necessary behavior of students, as well as a means of preventing and stopping inappropriate and useless actions. Let's look at the main groups and forms of demand.

The demands of the educator can be direct demands, in which they are aimed at students, the educator expects them to achieve certain actions, or the demands of the teacher are indirect demands, in which the teacher with his demands on students in relation to their peers. causes demands.

We first turn to the description of the main forms of demand, the choice of this or that form depends on the pedagogical situation. The pedagogical situation for direct demands arises from two basic conditions, two factors. The first factor is the attitude of the person to whom the request is made. The second factor is the student's response to the teacher's motivational activities. In general, we describe these relationships as positive, neutral, and negative, although in practice there can be many manifestations.

Let's talk about demand forms. The requirement can be straightforward, with the teacher's statement having a clear, bold statement in the form of a "do it and just do it" formula. In this case, the motivation for action is the demand itself.

Direct demand is especially effective in the first phase of teamwork. As one writer put it: "Without a sincere, transparent, convincing, passionate and determined demand, it is impossible to start educating the team, so it is necessary to work with those who are hesitant, who keep their promises. If he thinks of starting, he has made a mistake. "

There is also a need for educators to create new activities for students. It is noteworthy that the direct demand here is similar to the initial method of teaching, guidance. It should also be noted that direct demand is often used when a student is neutral about the teacher or the activity he or she is starting. In this case, it is especially important to follow the rules of direct demand.

The first rule is that the demand should be positive, that is, it should lead to a certain behavior, it should not simply prohibit or stop the actions of students. rules are used in different ways. However, the main content of the requirements of teachers is not prohibitions. The main thing in the requirements is a positive program of student behavior and activities.

The second rule is that the direct demand must be in the form of a guide, that is, it must be the same, clear and understandable, concrete. At first, when encouraging new student activities, the demand seems to be combined with guidance, which details and clearly describes the actions.

The third rule: any reasonable, clear and prepared request of the educator must be fulfilled, it must be completed. increases the strength and effectiveness of the requirements, forms a habit of clear obedience to the student-educator. And conversely, each unfulfilled requirement reduces the effectiveness of subsequent requirements. When it comes to the technical implementation of the right requirements, it is important to emphasize the firm, convincing tone of their implementation. He should be calm, serious depending on the situation, but never shout or insult the child. Requirement is

the expression of distrust in the mind of the pupil, and this or that behavior includes the teacher's recommendation for the teacher to make an independent decision on the appropriateness of solving the practical task in different ways. , they do not force the advice, the child has the right to choose. This form develops a conscious attitude to work and, moreover, teaches the educator to recognize himself as an adult friend, based on the fact that his reputation is hidden in a wide range of knowledge, vast life experience, skill. At the same time, the issue is not a guide that describes everything from thread to needle, but rather an incentive to seek solutions independently.

This form of direct demand is also useful in that it teaches students to consult with peers, students, in certain situations, especially when difficulties arise. Educators, in turn, need to teach them to

appreciate that students turn to counseling, not just to tell their response, but to provide natural help to their younger peers.

Demand is a hidden form and one of the most subtle means of inspiring students to take certain actions. Shama is a conditional abbreviation of a well-known requirement that has not been used before. An experienced educator is sometimes required to look, move eyebrows, and ask a rhetorical question to ensure that students perform the required actions. In certain circumstances, the candle plays the role of a "hidden" form of demand, which can be understood only by two people and does not attract the attention of others.

A conditional requirement is that a type of activity that is pleasing to the child is seen as an incentive for unpleasant or difficult activity.

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